

Accelerated remyelination and immune modulation by the EBI2 agonist 7 α ,25-dihydroxycholesterol analogue in the cuprizone model

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ABSTRACT

Summary: Research indicates a role for EBI2 receptor in remyelination, demonstrating that its deficiency or antagonism inhibits this process. However, activation of EBI2 with its endogenous ligand, oxysterol 7 α ,25-dihydroxycholesterol (7 α ,25OHC), does not enhance remyelination beyond the levels observed in spontaneously remyelinating tissue. We hypothesized that the short half-life of the natural ligand might explain this lack of beneficial effects and tested a synthetic analogue, CF₃-7 α ,25OHC, in the cuprizone model. The data showed that extending the bioavailability of 7 α ,25OHC is sufficient to accelerate remyelination *in vivo*. Moreover, the analogue, in contrast to the endogenous ligand, upregulated brain expression of *Ebi2* and the synthesis of 15 lipids in the mouse corpus callosum. Mechanistically, the increased concentration of oxysterol likely disrupted its gradient in demyelinated areas of the brain, leading to the dispersion of infiltrating EBI2-expressing immune cells rather than their accumulation in demyelinated regions. Remarkably, the analogue CF₃-7 α ,25OHC markedly decreased the lymphocyte and monocyte counts mimicking the key mechanism of action of some of the most effective disease-modifying therapies for multiple sclerosis. Furthermore, the *Cd4+* transcripts in the cerebellum and CD4+ cell number in the corpus callosum were reduced compared to vehicle-treated mice. These findings suggest a mechanism by which EBI2/7 α ,25OHC signalling modulates the immune response and accelerates remyelination *in vivo*.

1. Introduction

The Epstein Barr virus-induced gene 2 (EBI2, aka GPR183) is a membrane-bound G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) primarily expressed in the immune system, with the highest levels found in mature B and T cells [1–3]. The most potent endogenous agonist of EBI2 is an oxysterol 7 α ,25-dihydroxycholesterol (7 α ,25-OHC) synthesized enzymatically from cholesterol by cholesterol 25-hydroxylase (CH25H) and

25-hydroxycholesterol 7-alpha-hydroxylase (CYP7B1) and metabolised with hydroxy-delta-5-steroid dehydrogenase, 3 beta- and steroid delta-isomerase 7 (HSD3B7) [1,4]. Apart from its immune functions, EBI2 is also expressed and functional in central nervous system (CNS) cells, including astrocytes, microglia, and oligodendrocytes [5,6].

Together with its ligand, EBI2 has been implicated in several chronic inflammatory and autoimmune diseases, including inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), rheumatoid arthritis (RA), type 1 diabetes (T1D), and

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multiple sclerosis (MS) [3,7–11]. Specifically in MS, increased EBI2 expression was reported in infiltrating lymphocytes and glial cells inside MS plaques [3,10]. EBI2 expression was upregulated in memory lymphocytes in MS patients receiving natalizumab immunotherapy but not dimethyl fumarate [2]. Type 1 interferons, commonly used as a treatment for MS, induce CH25H, the first enzyme in the $7\alpha,25$ -OHC synthesis pathway [12]. Elevated concentrations of oxysterol 25OHC, the precursor to $7\alpha,25$ OHC, were found in the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) of patients with inflammatory CNS disease and were reduced in the plasma of relapsing-remitting MS patients [11]. A high-throughput RNA-sequencing (RNA-seq) study revealed differential expression of *EBI2* and *CH25H* in microglial cells, and *CYP7B1* in astrocytes, in MS brains. Additionally, *CYP7B1* was differentially expressed in the optic chiasm and *HSD3B7* in the corpus callosum [13].

The first study suggesting that EBI2/ $7\alpha,25$ OHC signalling might play a role in myelination found that during the early development, particularly around postnatal day 14, there was a delay in myelin basic protein (MBP) production in EBI2 knock-out (KO) pups [14]. These effects were observed *in vivo* and *ex vivo* in organotypic cerebellar slices. In the cuprizone model, we found that EBI2 KO mice exhibited greater demyelination and less efficient remyelination than wild types (WTs) [10]. Other studies indicated upregulated mRNA levels of the *Ch25h* enzyme in microglia during both the demyelinating and remyelinating phases in the cuprizone model [15]. An RNA-sequencing study found EBI2 to be one of the significantly downregulated genes specifically in oligodendrocytes during remyelination in the same model [13]. Taken together, these findings demonstrate an important regulatory role of

EBI2/ $7\alpha,25$ OHC signalling in myelination and remyelination in mice and humans. Here, we investigated a synthetic analogue of the EBI2 endogenous ligand $7\alpha,25$ OHC during remyelination in the cuprizone model.

2. Results

2.1. Barbadin inhibits $7\alpha,25$ OHC-induced internalisation of EBI2

MBP production is delayed in EBI2 KO mice around post-natal day 14 and long-term stimulation of EBI2 with $7\alpha,25$ OHC or its antagonism with NIBR189 blocks normal myelination in cerebellar slices prepared from post-natal pups [14]. Remyelination in the same organotypic slice model is inhibited in tissue treated with EBI2 antagonist NIBR189 while treatment with the agonist, $7\alpha,25$ OHC, does not enhance remyelination beyond the levels observed in untreated, spontaneously remyelinating slices [6]. To investigate whether these seemingly contradictory results are a consequence of EBI2 internalisation and consequent down-regulation after long-term stimulation with the agonist, we first tested whether barbadin, a selective β -arrestin/AP2 inhibitor blocks $7\alpha,25$ OHC-induced internalisation of EBI2 [16]. The data showed that barbadin blocked $7\alpha,25$ OHC-induced internalisation of EBI2 (Fig. 1a) and facilitated subsequent $7\alpha,25$ OHC-induced EBI2 signalling (Fig. 1b, c). Further, pre-treatment of cells with $7\alpha,25$ OHC or the antagonist NIBR189 inhibited subsequent Ca^{2+} release, while simultaneous pre-treatment with $7\alpha,25$ OHC and barbadin enabled Ca^{2+} release after subsequent addition of $7\alpha,25$ OHC.

Fig. 1. Barbadin inhibits $7\alpha,25$ OHC-induced endocytosis of EBI2. a. Treatment of human U937 monocytes with $7\alpha,25$ OHC induces EBI2 internalisation and co-treatment with barbadin blocks agonist-induced endocytosis. b. Schematic representation of the experimental setup of calcium imaging experiments. c. Traces showing increase in intracellular Ca^{2+} after addition of $7\alpha,25$ OHC and a corresponding bar graph (below) with corresponding microscopy images at baseline (0 seconds recording) and after addition of $7\alpha,25$ OHC (~35 seconds recording). One-way ANOVA and Sidak's multiple comparison tests, ****<0.0001, N=3.

2.2. Inhibition of 7 α ,25OHC-induced internalisation of EBI2 enhances remyelination in organotypic slices

Our previous studies indicated that treatment of LPC-demyelinated slices with 7 α ,25OHC does not enhance remyelination beyond the levels observed in non-treated slices [6]. We therefore here investigated whether co-treatment with barbadin and 7 α ,25OHC would keep EBI2 on the membrane, allow for sustained signalling and lead to enhanced remyelination in the slices (Fig. 2a,b). The data showed greater remyelination, that is an increase in *Cnpase* and *Mbp* mRNA transcripts, in slices co-treated with barbadin and 7 α ,25OHC (Fig. 2c). The *Ebi2* transcripts were downregulated in all LPC-treated slices similarly to *Cyp7b1* and *Hsd3b7*, the synthesising and degrading enzymes in the 7 α ,25OHC synthesis pathway (Fig. 2d). The *Ch25h* transcripts were modestly upregulated in the spontaneously remyelinating and 7 α ,25OHC-treated slices except for the NIBR189 treated slices where *Ch25h* transcripts were significantly downregulated.

2.3. Fluorinated 7 α ,25OHC (CF₃-7 α ,25OHC) accelerates remyelination in the cuprizone model

To validate the data obtained in the organotypic cerebellar slice

model, we tested barbadin in the cuprizone model (Fig. 3a). Oxysterols have very short half-lives *in vivo* rendering the use of the endogenous and unmodified oxysterol in animal models impractical. However, Deng and colleagues [17] synthesised an analogue of 7 α ,25OHC and tested it *in vivo*. This biostable fluorinated oxysterol after administration in mice via oral gavage had a half-life of elimination of 10 hours compared to approximately 30 minutes for the endogenous oxysterol. Here, we performed the cuprizone model and injected CF₃-7 α ,25OHC with or without barbadin during remyelination when mice were recovering on a normal diet. The data showed extensive demyelination in the corpus callosum in mice on the cuprizone diet for 9 weeks and substantial spontaneous remyelination in the remaining groups two weeks after cessation of the cuprizone diet (Fig. 3b, c). Co-administration of barbadin did not enhance remyelination beyond the levels observed in vehicle-treated mice, which remyelinate spontaneously. However, treatment with the fluoro analogue of 7 α ,25OHC (CF₃-7 α ,25OHC) alone enhanced remyelination beyond the levels observed in vehicle-treated mice. We subsequently validated these observations in LPC-demyelinated cerebellar slices, this time treated with CF₃-7 α ,25OHC. The data confirmed upregulated *Cnpase* transcripts only in CF₃-7 α ,25OHC treated slices (Supp. Fig. 1).

Fig. 2. Inhibition of agonist-induced endocytosis of EBI2 enhances remyelination in organotypic slices. a. Schematic representation of experimental setup. b. Synthesis pathway of 7 α ,25OHC. c. Quantification of *Cnpase*, *Mbp* and d. *Ebi2*, *Ch25h*, *Cyp7b1*, *Hsd3b7* mRNA levels in remyelinating organotypic slices. One sample t tests vs. non-treated ctrl * <0.05 , ** <0.01 , *** <0.001 . Values (ddCt) normalised to non-treated control.

Fig. 3. Fluorinated 7 α ,25OHC (CF₃-7 α ,25OHC) accelerates remyelination in the cuprizone model. **a.** Cuprizone model setup and treatment schedule. **b.** Representative images show central corpus callosum stained with luxol fast blue (scale 100 μ m) and **c.** a corresponding bar graph showing quantification of luxol staining. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (A vs. B), ***<0.001, N=8. Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA and Dunn's multiple comparison tests (C-F), *<0.05, N=8.

2.4. CF₃-7 α ,25OHC upregulates *Ebi2* in the brain in the cuprizone model

To investigate the mechanism driving the CF₃-7 α ,25OHC-induced enhanced remyelination, we examined its effects on cholesterol levels in the blood and brain. Cholesterol is the main component of myelin sheaths and the main endogenous EBI2 ligand, 7 α ,25OHC, is synthesised enzymatically from cholesterol (Fig. 4a, b). Analysis of the spatial distribution of cholesterol in the brain revealed a reduction in cholesterol content in the central corpus callosum (CC) in all mice which underwent the cuprizone diet. The data did not reveal significant differences in cholesterol content between spontaneously remyelinating (vehicle-treated, group C) and CF₃-7 α ,25OHC-treated (group E) mice but in contrast to the vehicle-treated group, there were no significant differences in cholesterol content between the control and CF₃-7 α ,25OHC-treated mice (Fig. 4c). Further analysis revealed upregulation of 15 lipid classes in CF₃-7 α ,25OHC-treated (group E) mice compared to vehicle-treated mice (Supp. Fig. 2). There were no effects of the cuprizone diet nor any of the treatments on cholesterol content in the blood (Supp. Fig. 3). The analysis of *Ebi2* and the enzymes involved in 7 α ,25OHC synthesis (*Ch25h*, *Cyp7b1*) and metabolism (*Hsd3b7*) revealed upregulation of *Ebi2* in CF₃-7 α ,25OHC-treated mice and no effect on the enzyme expression (Fig. 4d).

2.5. CF₃-7 α ,25OHC downregulates white blood cell infiltrate

EBI2 is one of the key immune system modulators with the highest expression in mature B and T lymphocytes [2]. We therefore examined the effects of increased levels of the EBI2 ligand on immune cells in the cuprizone model (Fig. 5a) and a short-term pharmacodynamics study. The data revealed a pronounced reduction in the white blood cell count in CF₃-7 α ,25OHC-treated mice in the cuprizone model with lymphocyte

numbers decreasing by 51 % and monocytes by 66 % (Fig. 5b). We then validated these effects of CF₃-7 α ,25OHC on white blood cell count by injecting normal mice with four doses of CF₃-7 α ,25OHC for 6, 12, 24 and 48 hours (Fig. 5c). The lymphocyte count was reduced already after 12 hours and a dose of 4 mg/kg and remained low after 48 hours in mice injected with the high dose of 100 mg/kg (Fig. 5d). Leucocyte count followed the same pattern (Supp Fig. 4). To examine the extent of immune cell infiltration in the brain, we quantified the CD4 mRNA transcripts in the cerebellum (Fig. 5e, f) and CD4+ cells in the corpus callosum (Fig. 5e, g). After nine weeks on the cuprizone diet, *Cd4* mRNA levels were reduced by 39 %. In vehicle-treated mice, these levels returned to those of non-cuprizone-fed mice after two weeks on a normal diet. Remarkably, in the CF₃-7 α ,25OHC-treated mice the level of *Cd4* transcripts in the cerebellum remained low, reduced by 36 %, after two weeks of recovery on normal diet. In the corpus callosum, the number of CD4+ cells increased in all cuprizone-fed mice but slightly less so in the CF₃-7 α ,25OHC-treated mice (Fig. 5g). Microglia and astrocyte numbers also increased in the corpus callosum in all cuprizone-fed mice (Supp Fig. 5a-c). While microglia numbers decreased in all treatment groups two weeks after cessation of the cuprizone diet (Supp Fig. 5b), astrocyte numbers did not display this trend remaining in high numbers in the corpus callosum after 2 weeks on normal diet (Supp Fig. 5c). The transcripts of the pro-inflammatory cytokine *Tnfa* in the cerebellum increased in cuprizone-fed mice and there was a statistically nonsignificant trend for reduction in the CF₃-7 α ,25OHC-treated animals (Supp Fig. 5d). The *Il1 β* transcripts were the least affected by the cuprizone diet (Supp Fig. 5e) and *Il6* transcripts decreased at 9 weeks of the cuprizone diet and were at similar levels to non-treated mice after two weeks of normal diet with no differences between the treatments (Supp Fig. 5f).

Fig. 4. CF₃-7 α ,25OHC upregulates *Ebi2* in the brain in the cuprizone model. **a.** Cuprizone model setup and treatments. **b.** Type of tissue analysis and 7 α ,25OHC synthesis pathway. **c.** Cuprizone downregulates *Ebi2* in the brain (cerebellum) and treatment with CF₃-7 α ,25OHC during remyelination upregulates its levels. The synthesising and degrading enzymes are unaffected. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (A vs. B), * <0.1 ($p=0.087$), $N=8$. ANOVA Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn's multiple comparison tests (C-F), * <0.1 ($p=0.051$), $N=8$. **d.** Spatial distribution of cholesterol ($m/z=369.3516$) in the mouse brain in the cuprizone model (groups A-F) and quantification in treated groups A, C and E. Also showing cholesterol distribution in magnified area of central part of CC. One-way ANOVA Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn's multiple comparison tests, * <0.05 , $N=3$ mice per group. Scale 1 mm.

3. Discussion

This study suggests a mechanism by which EB12/CF₃-7 α ,25OHC modulate remyelination that involves an increase in EB12 expression in the brain, a decrease in the white blood cell infiltrate and upregulation of lipid synthesis in the demyelinated areas. Our investigations thus far indicated that EB12/oxysterol signalling is involved in normal myelin development and remyelination but the data seemed contradictory and its interpretation proved complicated. Normal myelination was delayed in EB12 KO mice during postnatal days [14]. Both, long-term activation and inhibition of EB12 signalling during normal myelin development resulted in decreased myelination in cerebellar slices [14]. Persistent and long-term inhibition of EB12 signalling with the antagonist NIBR189 resulted in delayed remyelination and long-term treatment with the agonist, 7 α ,25OHC, did not enhance remyelination in cerebellar slices beyond the levels observed in non-treated tissue [6]. In the cuprizone model, EB12 KO mice remyelinated less efficiently than the WT mice [10]. Thus, neither blocking nor activating EB12 appeared to enhance normal myelination or remyelination. We speculated that these seemingly contradictory results were a consequence of receptor downregulation after prolonged agonist binding and an overall decrease in EB12 signalling, that is the same effect obtained with the antagonist or in EB12 KO mice. We hypothesised that blocking agonist-induced EB12

internalisation would enable a more sustained response to the oxysterol and induce intracellular signalling leading to enhanced remyelination. In 2017, a new small molecule which blocks the interaction between β -arrestin and the clathrin adaptor protein AP2 was characterized [16]. This selective β -arrestin/AP2 inhibitor, called barbadin, blocks agonist-induced internalisation of GPCRs whose internalisation is dependent on β -arrestin and the AP2 protein. Our previous data indicated that 7 α ,25OHC-induced internalisation of EB12 is dependent on β -arrestin type 2 and not type 1 [6]. Here, we could indeed demonstrate that barbadin not only blocks 7 α ,25OHC-induced internalisation of EB12 but also enables sustained activation of the receptor and intracellular signalling.

Having established that barbadin blocks 7 α ,25OHC-induced internalisation of EB12 we examined whether treating cerebellar slices with barbadin and 7 α ,25OHC would enhance remyelination. Indeed, in slices treated with barbadin and 7 α ,25OHC during remyelination, expression of *Cnpase* was the highest suggesting that increased EB12 signalling mediates for the therapeutic effects of 7 α ,25OHC, that is accelerated remyelination. Moreover, the downregulation of *Ebi2*, *Cyp7b1* and *Hsd3b7* transcripts in LPC-treated slices was observed. This is most likely a result of increased pro-inflammatory cytokine release induced by LPC [14] and linked to an increased CH25H synthesis under pro-inflammatory conditions shown by us and others before [18–20].

Fig. 5. $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ downregulates white blood cell infiltrate. **a.** Cuprizone model setup and treatment schedule. **b.** White blood cell total count after 14 days of treatment during remyelination in the cuprizone model. One-way ANOVA Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn's multiple comparison tests, ctrl $* < 0.05$ $** < 0.01$ $*** < 0.001$. **c.** Short-term pharmacokinetics experiment setup and **d.** lymphocyte total blood count. One sample t tests vs. non-treated ctrl normalised to 1 (green line). $* < 0.05$, $** < 0.01$, $*** < 0.001$. **e.** Type of tissue analysis performed and **f.** *Cd4* mRNA transcripts in the cerebellum. One-way ANOVA Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn's multiple comparison tests, $** < 0.01$. **g.** correlated total cell fluorescence (CTCF) of $CD4^+$ cells in the central corpus callosum after 14 days of treatment in the cuprizone model. Fluorescence in central CC below the background fluorescence in A gives negative values. Scale 100 μm . One-way ANOVA Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn's multiple comparison tests, $**** < 0.0001$.

Increased CH25H leads to increased $7\alpha,25OHC$ levels and a consequent EB12 internalisation and downregulation [18]. Here, the *Ch25h* transcripts were upregulated in the spontaneously remyelinating and $7\alpha,25OHC$ -treated slices but not in the antagonist NIB189-treated slices, where *Ch25h* transcripts were significantly downregulated. These data can explain why we previously observed inhibition of remyelination in NIB189-treated slices and in EB12 KO mice in the cuprizone model, as well as why $7\alpha,25OHC$ treatment alone did not enhance remyelination.

We then tested the effects of barbadin and $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ in the cuprizone model. Importantly, the biostable $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ alone enhanced remyelination beyond the levels observed in vehicle-treated mice. Following the extensive *in vitro* and *ex vivo* experiments, it was determined that barbadin is not required for the therapeutic effects of EB12/oxysterol on remyelination. This is most likely due to the prolonged bioavailability of the fluorinated oxysterol, which allowed for sustained EB12 receptor activation following receptor recycling to the plasma membrane and/or signaling from intracellular locations, as demonstrated earlier for S1P1 receptors and other GPCRs [21,22]. In summary, our findings further demonstrate that enhanced EB12 signaling promotes remyelination.

Initially, we hypothesized that the mechanism underlying $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ -enhanced remyelination involves its role in cholesterol metabolism. While $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ did not significantly increase cholesterol content in central corpus callosum beyond the levels observed in vehicle-treated mice, its levels were also not significantly different to those observed in non-treated controls indicating a modest involvement in the regulation of cholesterol content during remyelination in the cuprizone model. Moreover, $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ upregulated 15 lipid classes in the corpus callosum (Supp Fig. 2) indicating increased lipid synthesis in this brain region during remyelination in $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ treated mice. Moreover, investigations of EB12 and the enzymes involved in $7\alpha,25OHC$ synthesis from cholesterol (*Ch25h*, *Cyp7b1*) and its subsequent metabolism (*Hsd3b7*) revealed significant upregulation of *Ebi2* in $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ -treated mice and no effect on the enzyme expression demonstrating that the mechanism is not

cholesterol- but EB12-dependent. $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ upregulated *Ebi2* during remyelination in the cuprizone model while in slices, the natural ligand $7\alpha,25OHC$, did not exert effects on *Ebi2* expression and did not enhance remyelination beyond the effects observed in untreated slices indicating differential effects of the synthetic analogue and an EB12-dependent mechanism in remyelination. Less importantly, we noted differential effects of LPC in slices and the cuprizone diet on enzyme expression and pro-inflammatory signalling. Cuprizone did not modulate the enzyme expression nor pro-inflammatory cytokine levels while LPC highly modulated cytokine levels and enzyme expression [14].

Subsequently, we reasoned that if the effects on remyelination exerted by $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ are not mediated via a cholesterol-related mechanism it may be the immune regulation. EB12 is one of the key modulators of the immune responses with the highest expression in mature B and T lymphocytes [2]. Here, during remyelination EB12 expression in the brain increased and even more so in $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ -treated mice. The $CD4^+$ cell numbers also increased in all cuprizone-fed mice in the corpus callosum, which is the area of greatest demyelination and most likely the highest oxysterol gradient attracting the EB12-expressing $CD4^+$ cells to the corpus callosum. Importantly, there were slightly fewer $CD4^+$ cells in the corpus callosum than in the vehicle-treated mice possibly indicating a reverse trend where EB12 expression increases and $CD4^+$ cell numbers decrease which can be explained by equal distribution of $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ in the brains and disruption of the oxysterol gradient formation resulting in more equal dispersion of immune cells rather than their accumulation in highly demyelinated areas such as the corpus callosum in the cuprizone model. A disruption of the $7\alpha,25OHC$ gradient in the brain leading to the dispersion of lymphocytes instead of their accumulation in demyelinating areas may be another mechanism by which treatment with $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ may be beneficial in MS. However, most remarkably, the data revealed that $CF_3-7\alpha,25OHC$ strongly downregulates *Cd4* mRNA levels in the brain and white blood cell count imitating the mechanism of action of some of the most effective disease-modifying therapies (DMTs) for MS. For instance, fingolimod reduces lymphocyte count by 70 % in

the two weeks following treatment initiation in humans [23]. This reduction in lymphocytes in the blood and brain also explains the reduced *Cd4* transcripts in the cerebellum in CF₃-7 α ,25OHC-treated mice where CF₃-7 α ,25OHC leads to an overall depletion of lymphocytes. Most, if not all, DMTs for MS, modulate the immune system either by downregulating pro-inflammatory signalling, reducing immune cell numbers or their passage to the CNS. Reduction of circulating immune cell numbers and disruption of oxysterol gradient in the brain is most likely the mechanism of CF₃-7 α ,25OHC while its effects on pro-inflammatory cytokine expression in the brain or glial (microglia, astrocyte) numbers were non-significant both concerning the cuprizone diet alone and CF₃-7 α ,25OHC treatment. These findings suggest a mechanism by which EBI2/CF₃-7 α ,25OHC modulate remyelination and may have therapeutic value in the treatment of MS.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Aleksandra Rutkowska has patent #EP24191137.9 pending to n/a. Bartosz Karaszewski has patent #EP24191137.9 pending to n/a. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies were not used in the writing process

Materials availability

There are restrictions to the availability of CF₃-7 α ,25OHC due to the lack of an external centralized repository for its distribution and our need to maintain the stock. We are glad to share CF₃-7 α ,25OHC with reasonable compensation by requestor for its processing and shipping.

Materials & methods

Cuprizone model

All protocols involving animals were approved by the Local Ethical Committee for Animal Experiments in Bydgoszcz (Poland) following national and international guidelines and ethical regulations for animal care and use in research. The cuprizone model was approved under permission number 38/2022. All mice were maintained in a pathogen-free animal facility under standard animal room conditions: temperature 20–23 °C; humidity 55 %–60 %; 12-hour light/dark cycle and air exchange 15x/hour. Forty-eight 6–9 week old male C57BL/6 mice were used in the experiment with 8 mice per group. Out of the six treatment groups, five groups were fed chow pellets with reduced copper content supplemented with 0.2 % cuprizone (bis(cyclohexanone)oxalaldihydrazone), #AIN93G, Ssniff) for 9 weeks. The sixth group was on a standard diet (pellets with reduced copper content) for 9 weeks (#AIN93G, Ssniff). After 9 weeks, group B (N=8, group B) from the cuprizone-fed mice and the mice (N=8) on the standard diet (group A) were anaesthetised with isoflurane and perfused. The remaining four groups of mice returned to a normal diet (#AIN93G, Ssniff) and started receiving daily injections for two weeks. Barbadin (0.3 mg/kg, SML3127, Merck) or its vehicle (1 % DMSO, vehicle #1) were injected intraperitoneally (ip) one hour before CF₃-7 α ,25OHC (20 mg/kg) or its vehicle (canola oil, vehicle #2), which were injected subcutaneously (sc). Group C received vehicle #1 followed by vehicle #2, group D received barbadin followed by vehicle #2, group E received vehicle #1 followed by CF₃-7 α ,25OHC and group F received barbadin followed by CF₃-7 α ,25OHC. After two weeks all mice were anaesthetised with isoflurane and perfused. Blood was collected in EDTA tubes from the heart during perfusion from groups C-F. A blood count was performed immediately after blood collection and the remaining blood samples were centrifuged, plasma collected and frozen at –20 °C until further analysis (see biochemistry section for details). After perfusion cerebella were separated from the rest of the brain and snap-frozen for qPCR analysis. The hemispheres were prepared for immunohistological staining (see the luxol fast blue staining section for details).

Short-term pharmacokinetics model

The protocol was approved by the Local Ethical Committee for Animal Experiments in Bydgoszcz (Poland) following national and international guidelines and ethical regulations under permission number Nr 34/2023. All mice were maintained in a pathogen-free animal facility under standard animal room conditions: temperature 20–23 °C; humidity 55 %–60 %; 12-hour light/dark cycle and air exchange 15x/hour. 160 6–9 week old male C57BL/6 mice were used in the experiment with 8 mice per treatment group. Mice were injected sc with either vehicle (canola oil) or CF₃-7 α ,25OHC at doses 0.8 mg/kg, 4 mg/kg, 20 mg/kg or 100 mg/kg and sacrificed after 6, 12, 24 or 48 hours after injection. All mice were anaesthetised with isoflurane and blood was collected from the heart. About 300 μ l of whole blood was allowed to clot then centrifuged and serum was frozen at –80 °C for further biochemical analysis (see blood biochemistry section for details). About 200 μ l of remaining whole blood was collected in EDTA tubes and sent to a commercial animal laboratory for blood count. The brains were split into two hemispheres, snap-frozen and kept for subsequent qPCR analysis (see qPCR section for details).

Organotypic cerebellar slice model

Organotypic cerebellar slices were prepared from 10-day-old (P10) C57BL/6 mice according to previously published protocol [14]. Briefly, pups were decapitated with scissors, the skull was opened, and the cerebellum was removed and placed in cold Opti-MEM medium (11058021, Invitrogen). Parasagittal 400 μm thick slices of the cerebellum were cut using the McIlwain tissue chopper (WPI, USA) and then separated using needles under a dissection microscope. Four to six slices were cultured on a single insert (Merck, Millicell, PICM03050) in a humidified incubator at 35.5 °C and 5 % CO₂ for 14 days *in vitro* (DIV). The growth medium consisted of 50 % Opti-MEM (11058-021, Gibco), 25 % Hanks' buffered salt solution (HBSS, 21-022-CV), 25 % heat-inactivated horse serum (26050088, LifeTechnologies) supplemented with Glutamax (2 mM, 35050-061, Gibco), D-glucose (28 mM, G8769, Merck), 1 % pen/strep (30-002-CI, Corning) and HEPES (10 mM, 25-060-CI, Corning). After 14 DIVs, slices were placed in treatment media (Neurobasal A (10888-022, Gibco), B27 (2 %, 17504001, Gibco), Glutamax (2 mM, 35050061, Gibco), D-glucose (28 mM, G8769, Merck), 1 % pen/strep (30-002-CI, Corning) and HEPES (10 mM, 25-060-CI, Corning)) supplemented with lysophosphatidylcholine (LPC, 0.4 mg/mL, L-4129, Merck) for 18 hours at 35.5 °C. Slices were then moved to fresh treatment media for 30 hours to allow for demyelination, and then moved to fresh media supplemented with barbadin (16 μM) or 7 α ,25OHC (0.1 μM) or CF₃-7 α ,25OHC (0.1 μM) or NIBR189 (10 μM) for approximately 20 DIVs. After 20 DIVs, the slices were collected for subsequent qPCR analysis (see qPCR section for details).

EBI2 internalisation in U937 monocytes

Human monocyte U937 cells were grown in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with Glutamax, 10 % FBS, 1 % MEM non-essential amino acids (NEA, Invitrogen, 11140), 1 % sodium pyruvate (Invitrogen, 11360-070), 1 % pen/strep and 0.1 % 2-Mercaptoethanol (Merck, M7154) in T75 culture flasks. For EBI2 internalisation experiments cells were starved for 3 hours before incubation with 7 α ,25OHC (1 μM) for 1 hour. Barbadin (100 μM , SML3127, Merck) was added 20 minutes before 7 α ,25OHC. Cells were washed twice with PBS and fixed with ice-cold 4 % PFA for 10 minutes on ice. PFA was removed, the cells were washed with PBS twice and incubated in a blocking solution (5 % FCS, 1 % BSA, 0.1 % Tween-20) for 30 minutes at room temperature. Primary mouse anti-EBI2 antibody (clone 57C9B51C9, Novartis) was diluted in the blocking solution and cells were incubated for two hours at room temperature on a rocker. After washing three times in PBS the cells were incubated in goat anti-mouse Alexa Fluor 546 (Invitrogen, A-11003) and Hoechst 33342 (Invitrogen, H1399) in blocking solution for one hour on a rocker. After washing and mounting on cover slides the cells were imaged with a confocal microscope Zeiss LSM 880 (Germany).

Live cell calcium imaging

For live cell calcium imaging experiments U937 monocytes were seeded onto 24 mm culture glass coverslips coated with poly-d-lysine. Cells were incubated in HBSS (no phenol red) supplemented with 10 mM glucose and 25 mM HEPES with 7.5 μM Cal-520 calcium dye (ab171868) for 60 min at 37 °C. Cells were then pre-treated with barbadin (16 μM , SML3127, Merck), NIBR189 (10 μM , gift from Novartis) or 7 α ,25OHC (1 μM , gift from Novartis) for 30 minutes. The coverslips with cells were inserted into AttoFluor chambers (ThermoFisher, A7816) for imaging using a confocal Zeiss LSM 880 microscope. The calcium signal was recorded for 180 seconds in total and 7 α ,25OHC (1 μM) was added 30 seconds after the start of recording. The increase in mean fluorescence intensity was analysed with ImageJ and the area under the curve (AUC) was calculated with GraphPad Prism. The data was normalised to the baseline reading before the addition of

7 α ,25OHC.

Luxol fast blue staining and quantification

Upon removal from the skull and separation of the cerebellum, the brain hemispheres were briefly washed in ice-cold PBS and fixed in 4 % PFA for 24 hours at 4 °C. Following fixation, the brains were cryopreserved in a 15 % sucrose solution for 24 hours, followed by overnight immersion in a 30 % sucrose solution. The fixed brains were embedded in OCT (Leica; 14020108926) and cryosectioned into 30 μm coronal sections using a cryostat (Thermo Fisher) at -21 °C. Serial sections were stored in a cryoprotective medium at -20 °C until further analysis. For luxol fast blue (LFB) staining, sections from three distinct parts of the brain, corresponding to the rostral part, body, and caudal part of the corpus callosum (CC), were selected. The sections were washed with PBS, thaw-mounted on glass slides, immersed in decreasing concentrations of ethanol and stained overnight with a 0.1 % LFB solution (Sigma Aldrich, LO294). After differentiation in a 0.05 % lithium carbonate solution and 70 % ethanol, the sections were dehydrated in absolute ethanol, dried, and coverslipped. High-resolution optical images were captured using a Zeiss microscope at 10x and 20x magnification. Optical myelin density was evaluated in the central part of the CC (covering the area up to 500 μm from midline) using densitometry analysis with automated thresholding in ImageJ software, according to the methods developed previously [24,25].

Immunohistochemistry

Free-floating slices were rinsed twice with PBS and fixed in ice-cold 100 % methanol for 5 minutes. Following fixation, the slices were incubated in a blocking solution consisting of 10 % BSA, 0.5 % Triton X-100, and 1 % NGS in PBS for 24 hours at room temperature. After blocking, the slices were treated with the primary antibody solution (2 % BSA, 0.1 % Triton X-100 in PBS) and incubated overnight at 4 °C. The primary antibodies were rabbit anti-gial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP, Cell Signalling, cat. nr. 12389, RRID: AB_2827276), rabbit anti-Iba1 (WAKO, cat. nr. 019-19741, RRID: AB_839504), and rabbit CD4 (Bioss, Cat. Nr. bs-0647R, RRID: AB_10859521). Post-incubation, the slices were washed three times for 30 minutes each in PBS before being incubated in a secondary antibody solution containing anti-rabbit Cy3-conjugated antibody (Jackson ImmunoResearch, 111-165-144) or Alexa 488 (Jackson ImmunoResearch, BA-0647R) for 4 hours in the dark. The slices were then counterstained with a Hoechst 33342 solution (Invitrogen, H1399), followed by washing and mounting on glass slides. High-resolution images were captured using a Zeiss LSM880 confocal microscope (Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany) and analyzed with Zeiss Zen 3.5 software. The quantification of GFAP- and IBA-positive cells in the central and lateral regions of the corpus callosum was performed automatically using the particle counter tool in ImageJ software.

Quantitative PCR (qPCR)

Cerebellar slices were collected in 400 μl of fozozol following experiments. Frozen cerebella from the cuprizone model were homogenized with a dounce homogenizer in 400 μl of fozozol. A total RNA mini plus kit (036-100, AA Biotech) was used to isolate RNA from the samples. cDNA was synthesised with the high-capacity cDNA reverse transcription kit (4368814, ThermoFisher) following the manufacturer's protocol: 10 minutes at 25 °C followed by 120 minutes at 37 °C and 5 seconds at 85 °C. TaqMan fast advanced master mix (4444557, ThermoFisher) was used to perform real-time (RT)-qPCR on the Light-Cycler480 (Roche): 5 minutes at 95 °C, then 40 cycles with first 20 seconds at 95 °C followed by 45 seconds at 60 °C and a final step for 30 seconds at 40 °C. The following Taqman (Applied Biosystems) mouse primers were used: β -actin (Mm02619580_g1), Ebi2 (Mm02620906_s1), Ch25h (Mm00515486_s1), Cyp7b1 (Mm00484157_m1), Hsd3b7

(Mm01159156_g1), *Cnpase* (Mm01306640_m1), *Mbp* (Mm01266402_m1), *Cd4* (Mm00442754_m1), *Trfa* (Mm00443258_m1), *Il6* (Mm00446190_m1) and *Il1b* (Mm00434228_m1). Relative gene expression for cerebellar slices was determined with the ΔCt based on absolute quantification after normalisation to the housekeeping gene. Cerebellum gene expression was further normalised to the control condition with a normal diet ($\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}$).

Total cholesterol and blood count analysis

Total cholesterol levels in serum samples from cuprizone model groups C, D, E and F were analysed using a colorimetric enzymatic (CHOD-POD) method with a measuring range from 0 mg/dl to 900 mg/dl (Tersaco, Switzerland, T-6011). The reaction was carried out on a Santhia240 Premium biochemistry analyser (Tersaco, Switzerland). To monitor the performance of assay procedures: a multiCONTROL Clin-Chem 1 control sample was used (Tersaco, Switzerland, T-8077).

Mass spectrometry imaging of brain slices

Mass spectrometry imaging (MSI) was performed on 30 μm thick mouse brain slices corresponding to slice 69 in Allen reference mouse brain atlas using an AP-MALDI source (MassTech) coupled to an Orbitrap Exploris 480 mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific). Briefly, tissue slices were washed twice with ultrapure water and air-dried on Opti-TOF plates (MassTech), then coated with CHCA using a SunChrom SunCollect sprayer (SunChrom). Spectra were acquired in positive ionization in 20 μm lateral and 240,000 mass resolution over the 300–1500 m/z range. Raw spectra were converted to imzML and imported to LipostarMSI (Mass Analytica). LFB stainings from consecutive slices were used for histology-based region of interest (ROI) annotation of corpus callosum. Signal intensities were normalized to root-mean squares. Average area intensities of ROIs were exported for statistical analysis at 2 ppm mass tolerance. Lipids were putatively annotated using accurate mass at 1 ppm tolerance and cross-validated with previously published data [26,27].

Synthesis of CF₃-7 α ,25OHC

To synthesize cholest-5-ene-7 β -trifluoromethyl-3 β ,7 α ,25-triol (CF₃-7 α ,25OHC), we employed modified synthetic protocols initially reported by Deng X. et al. [17]. First, commercially available 25-hydroxycholesterol (25OHC) was reacted with benzoyl chloride in anhydrous pyridine to produce cholest-5-ene-3 β ,25-diol 3 β ,25-dibenzoate with nearly quantitative yield (Scheme S1). In the subsequent step, challenges including irreproducibility and suboptimal conversion rates were encountered with the manganese(III)-catalyzed allylic oxidation method. Consequently, we adopted an alternative oxidation strategy using pyridinium chlorochromate (Scheme S2) in anhydrous benzene, as described in the literature, achieving the desired ketone with improved efficiency [28]. The introduction of the trifluoromethyl group was accomplished using the Ruppert-Prakash reagent in the presence of catalytic amounts of cesium fluoride. The resulting mixture of silyl-protected alcohols was subsequently deprotected using a 1 M TBAF solution in THF, yielding two diastereoisomeric products (Scheme S3). These were successfully separated via column chromatography. In the final stage, the benzoyl-protecting groups were removed using a potassium hydroxide/methanol mixture (Scheme S4). The target compound, CF₃-7 α ,25OHC, was then purified through recrystallization. The structure of obtained compounds was confirmed using NMR spectroscopy (Figure S1-S4) and the determination of melting points.

Statistics

All statistical analysis was performed with GraphPad Prism 9 applying Kolmogorov-Smirnov t-test for comparisons of two groups,

one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) for comparisons of three or more groups followed by Dunn's, Tukey's or Sidak's multiple comparisons post-hoc tests or one-sample t-test for comparisons of three or more groups to normalised control. Data are shown as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Robust regression and Outlier removal (ROUT) method was applied to identify and remove outliers. Significant effects are indicated by asterisks where * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$ signifies statistically significant results, unless otherwise specified in the figure legend.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.biopha.2024.117653.

Data Availability

The data supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors, without undue reservation, to any qualified researcher.

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